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DMP: Performance- Evaluation of different Classifiers

PEC

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Version:	1.0
Status:	ongoing
Dissemination level:	PU: Public
Document link:	

Loan Classification Experiment has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Loan Classification Experiment project. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project.

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DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
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Reviewed by:			
Approved by:			

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
1.0	26.04.2025	-	Jonas Tatzberger

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
kB	kilobyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Jonas Tatzberger will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	loan-dataset	DOI: 10.82556/nje3-ch34	CC0-1.0	no

The reused dataset is of tabular structure (it was originally a csv-file). The generated data will include trained classification models which will be exported as a pkl (pickle) datatype. Additionally several graphs will be generated as png image files and a final prediction of the test set will be output as a csv file.

The reused data is used to train classification models for education purposes (learning how to train models/parameter tuning, etc.).

The re-used data has 10.000 rows and a total size of about 16-17kB. The generated data is of various sizes with all (except one trained model) having sizes of <100kB.

The data was originally provided as part of a university lecture and was now uploaded to TU Wien dbrepo to make it accessible more easily.

The generated data/models might be useful to other students in order to train their own models on the data and compare their results with this project.

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

title	source	rights (e.g. license)	type
performance-evaluation-of-classifiers	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15290485	MIT	GitHub-Repository

In this project, no new research data will be generated. Instead, an existing dataset will be reused to train and evaluate multiple classification models. Before model training, several preprocessing steps are applied to prepare the data. These steps include separating the dataset into numerical and categorical features, identifying and removing duplicate rows, checking for missing (NaN) values, and deleting columns that contain only a single unique value. All data handling and analysis are performed using the Python programming language. The main libraries used are pandas for data manipulation, numpy for numerical operations, scikit-learn (sklearn) for machine learning modeling and preprocessing, and matplotlib for visualization during data exploration. These methods ensure the data is cleaned, structured, and appropriately processed for robust model development and evaluation.

Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Students and general public

Results

The results are uploaded to TU Wien research data; DOI: [10.70124/d4wh0-yn586](https://doi.org/10.70124/d4wh0-yn586)

2.FAIR data

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

Since no metadata was provided with the original dataset (it was only a csv file), no additional metadata (apart from the title, etc.) will be provided, since it is not available.

The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.

Repository description: The used repository is the TU Wien dbrepo, where the data is assigned a PID (persistent identifier) and is resolved to a digital object.

All data is made openly available without any embargoes.

The data is available for free on the TU Wien dbrepo for everybody, because of this, the identities of the persons accessing the data will not be monitored and there is no need for a data access committee.

The metadata will be openly available and licenced under CC0.

The data will remain available and findable for at least 10 years after the completion of this project. In case the data will be unavailable at some point after this timeframe, the metadata will continue to be visible and a message indicating the absence of the data will be displayed.

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Since the data is provided as a table which was originally in csv format, it can be exported as such (by downloading it from the repository) and be processed with any commonly available tool which can handle this datatype (e.g. Excel, LibreCalc, various programming languages, etc.)

Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

No uncommon ontologies/vocabularies are created.

No other data is references in the used data.

Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to the published material. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Code Documentation: All scripts used for data preprocessing, model training, and evaluation will be clearly commented. Additionally, a data flow diagram is provided to make the process easier to understand. The code will be organized into logical steps and stored in version-controlled repositories (e.g., GitHub), ensuring transparency and reproducibility. Environment Information: A list of all software libraries (pandas, numpy, scikit-learn, matplotlib) and their versions will be provided through a requirements.txt file. Data Source Reference: Clear references to the original dataset, licensing conditions, and any modifications made to the dataset during preprocessing, will be provided.

No data collection is done as part of this project, the only outputs are models/predictions/images derived from the reused data.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

The code that is used to train the models will also be published. This is done using a GitHub repository, where all needed data and the requirements will be provided. The published code is licenced using the MIT licence.

In order ensure the FAIR principles, the repository will have a DOI which is published alongside the other outputs. To make the data accessible, a detailed readme-file is provided in the repository in which the requirements to run the code are specified. To make this setup easy, an additional file is provided which specifies the modules (and their versions) that are needed in order to set up the running environment.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with Jonas Tatzberger (e12002213@student.tuwien.ac.at) being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Coordinator (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will not be stored on TU Wien servers.

R1 (loan-dataset) will be stored on TU Wien dbrepo, which is also where regular backups will be generated.

Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only

Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
R1	TU Wien dbrepo	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Jonas Tatzberger: read/write access to all datasets

Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No.